

Uniform Colour-Separated Windmill Patterns with Pairwise Distinct Branch Colours on the $4 \times 4 \times 4$ Rubik's Cube

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Abstract: The Rubik's Cube has long attracted mathematical interest, with much research focusing on its group-theoretic and structural properties. Some authors have also examined aesthetic questions, namely how colours may be arranged on the cube to produce patterns that are both visually appealing and legally realisable. This paper explores both aspects by introducing a new family of designs on the $4 \times 4 \times 4$ Rubik's Cube, referred to as uniform windmill patterns, in which each face displays a windmill figure of identical orientation. Using elementary combinatorial and structural reasoning, we show that there exist exactly 64 distinct legal uniform windmill patterns and provide explicit algorithms to obtain them. We then introduce and analyse the concept of total symmetry. A uniform windmill pattern satisfies total symmetry precisely when the corresponding algorithms are independent of the cube's initial orientations. Finally, we show that among the 64 legal uniform windmill patterns, exactly two are totally symmetric, illustrating the rarity of perfect symmetry and balance.

1 Introduction

Rubik's Cubes are an engaging puzzle for people of all ages. Cube enthusiasts may be interested either in speedcubing or in creating artistic patterns on cubes. It has also inspired a wide range of mathematical investigations, from recreational explorations to more theoretical studies (for instance, [1], [2], [3], and [4]). This article seeks to strike a balance between mathematics and aesthetics by presenting a new kind of artistic pattern and developing the complete mathematical theory underlying it.

Even-order cubes, such as the $4 \times 4 \times 4$, have a significantly greater number of visual configurations, since their centre cubies can move independently. This additional degree of freedom enables the creation of a wide variety of aesthetically pleasing and mathematically interesting colour arrangements. The author has long been interested in designing colour-separated windmill patterns on the $4 \times 4 \times 4$ Rubik's Cube, in which the four branches of each windmill have pairwise distinct colours. Figures 1(a) and 1(b) illustrate two possible orientations of such a windmill on a single face of the cube. Here C_1, \dots, C_5 denote different colours: C_1 represents the background colour, while C_2, \dots, C_5 correspond to the four branches of the windmill.

In this article, we define the windmill shown in Figure 1(a) as **clockwise**, and that in Figure 1(b) as **anticlockwise**. A **colour-separated** pattern means that visually similar (or opposite) colours do not appear adjacent to one another. In the standard Rubik's Cube colour scheme — red, orange, blue, green, white, and yellow — each colour is

opposite to a visually similar one: red-orange, blue-green, and white-yellow. Hence, if a branch of a windmill is red, its background should not be red or orange; likewise, a blue branch should not have a blue or green background, and a white branch should not have a white or yellow background, etc.

Figure 1: Two ways to display a windmill pattern on one face of the $4 \times 4 \times 4$ Rubik's Cube. (a) The clockwise orientation. (b) The anticlockwise orientation.

While it is straightforward to construct such a windmill pattern on a single face (see Figure 2), achieving a uniform design — where every face of the cube exhibits a windmill of the same orientation — requires additional structural considerations. To formalise this idea, we first clarify the meanings of several fundamental concepts. Unless otherwise stated, the terminology used in this paper follows that of [2].

Figure 2: A face of the $4 \times 4 \times 4$ Rubik's Cube displaying the figure of a clockwise windmill.

The elementary three-dimensional components that form the surface of the $4 \times 4 \times 4$ Rubik's Cube are called **cubies**. The cube contains a total of 56 cubies: 24 centre cubies, 24 edge cubies, and 8 corner cubies. According to the positions and orientations of the cubies in a given configuration, each corner or edge cubie is assigned an **orientation** value: for every edge cubie, the orientation is defined modulo 2 [2, p12], and for every corner cubie, it is defined modulo 3 [2, p3].

For example, consider a solved standard Rubik's Cube, with the yellow face taken as the front face and the red face as the upper face. In this orientation, all corner cubies have orientation value 0. If a corner cubie is rotated through 120° clockwise while remaining in its original position, its orientation value changes. For further details, see [2, p3].

In Figure 3, two green-red edge cubies are respectively circled and boxed. Under legal moves of the $4 \times 4 \times 4$ Rubik's Cube — such as face turns, slice turns, and global

rotations — it is impossible to move the boxed cubie to the position originally occupied by the circled one while keeping its green sticker on the upper face. If the cube is disassembled and the boxed cubie is manually placed in that position with its green sticker still facing upward, then the cubie’s orientation changes to 1. For the precise formal definition of edge orientations, see [2, p12]; we do not reproduce it here.

Figure 3: The solved state of the $4 \times 4 \times 4$ Rubik’s Cube, in which two green-red edge cubies are highlighted: one is circled and the other boxed.

A **configuration** of the Rubik’s Cube refers to a particular arrangement of all cubies on the cube. Each cubie must be used exactly once. Given two configurations C_1 and C_2 , if there exists some cubie whose position or orientation in C_1 differs from that in C_2 , then C_1 and C_2 are regarded as distinct configurations, even if they can be transformed into each other by a global rotation of the entire cube. For the precise formal definition of a configuration, see [2, p4].

It is a well-known mathematical fact that, under legal transformations (such as face turns, inner-slice turns and global rotations), certain configurations of the $4 \times 4 \times 4$ Rubik’s Cube cannot be reached [2, p4 & p13]. A configuration of the cube is called **legal** if it can be obtained from the solved state by a finite sequence of legal moves, without actions like disassembling the cube and reattaching the cubies [2, p4].

We now introduce a new term of our own. A **pattern** (or **relative colour arrangement**) on the $4 \times 4 \times 4$ Rubik’s Cube is an assignment of colours to all stickers on the cube, without requiring the arrangement to be physically attainable by legal moves. For example, all stickers on all faces may be coloured white, and additional colours not appearing on a standard Rubik’s Cube (such as black) may be used. The word “relative” indicates that two relative colour arrangements are regarded as the same if one can be obtained from the other by a rotation of the entire cube.

We say that a configuration **represents** a pattern (or relative colour arrangement) if the configuration visually corresponds to that pattern. Different configurations may represent the same relative colour arrangement. For example, if two configurations can be transformed into one another by a global rotation of the cube, then they represent the same pattern.

A pattern on the $4 \times 4 \times 4$ Rubik’s Cube is said to be **legal** if it can be represented by at least one legal configuration of the cube. Note that an illegal configuration may nevertheless represent a legal pattern. Indeed, let C_1 be a legal configuration of the $4 \times 4 \times 4$ Rubik’s Cube. According to Theorem 6.5 on page 13 of [2], if another configuration C_2 is obtained by swapping two centre cubies of the same colour in C_1 , while keeping

all other cubies fixed, then C_2 is an illegal configuration. However, C_1 and C_2 represent the same pattern. Hence, the given relative colour arrangement is considered legal.

Definition 1.1. A **uniform clockwise colour-separated windmill pattern with pairwise distinct branch colours** on the $4 \times 4 \times 4$ Rubik's Cube is a relative colour arrangement involving only colours existing on the cube, such that the following conditions are satisfied:

1. On every face, there are five pairwise distinct colours C_1, \dots, C_5 , arranged in the way shown in Figure 1(a), forming the image of a clockwise windmill.
2. None of the colour pairs red–orange, blue–green, and white–yellow may appear as the background and a windmill branch on the same face.

The uniform anticlockwise version is defined analogously. In what follows, we focus on the clockwise case, since all principal results — such as the enumeration of legal patterns — apply symmetrically to the anticlockwise case as well. Henceforth, the term “**uniform windmill pattern**” will refer to a uniform clockwise colour-separated windmill pattern with pairwise distinct branch colours on the $4 \times 4 \times 4$ Rubik's Cube. Throughout the paper, we assume that the solved state of the cube under consideration is Figure 4(a). A valid uniform windmill pattern is illustrated in Figure 4(b).

Figure 4: (a) The planar net of a completed $4 \times 4 \times 4$ Rubik's Cube. (b) The planar net of a $4 \times 4 \times 4$ Rubik's Cube with a valid uniform windmill pattern.

The paper first establishes that there are precisely 64 different legal uniform windmill patterns. It then provides explicit algorithms to generate these patterns. Finally, the article introduces the notion of total symmetry, linking it to the work presented in [3], and proves that there are only two distinct legal uniform windmill patterns that satisfy total symmetry.

2 Enumerating Legal Uniform Windmill Patterns

According to Theorem 6.5 on Page 13 of [2], a configuration of the $4 \times 4 \times 4$ Rubik's Cube is legal if and only if the following three conditions are met:

1. The orientation of every edge cubie is 0.
2. The orientations of all the eight corner cubies sum to 0 modulo 3.
3. Note that the transition of the cube from the solved state to the given configuration corresponds to a permutation of its cubies, in which centre cubies may only be exchanged with other centre cubies, and corner cubies only with other corner cubies. The third condition then requires that the parity of the permutation of the centre cubies is the same as that of the permutation of the corner cubies.

Theorem 2.1. *A pattern A on the $4 \times 4 \times 4$ Rubik's Cube is legal if and only if there exists a configuration C of the cube representing A such that:*

1. *the orientation of every edge cubie in C is 0, and*
2. *the orientations of all the eight corner cubies in C sum to 0 modulo 3.*

Proof. The “only if” direction follows immediately from Theorem 6.5 in [2]. Conversely, suppose that there exists a configuration C representing A which satisfies the two conditions stated above. If the parity of the permutation of the centre cubies in terms of C is the same as that of the permutation of the corner cubies, then C is a legal configuration and we are done. Otherwise, let C_1 be the configuration obtained from C by swapping two centre cubies of the same colour. Then by Theorem 6.5 in [2], C_1 is a legal configuration that also represents A . Hence, A is legal. \square

We then discuss the properties of corner cubies that must be satisfied by a legal uniform windmill pattern. If a pattern requires the existence of a corner cubie that contains two stickers of the same colour, or two colours that are opposite to each other in the solved state of the cube, then such a pattern is certainly not legal.

Figure 5: Assume the planar net of the cube under consideration looks like Figure 4(a) in the solved state. (a) The corner cubie containing the three colours red, green, and white. (b) A corner cubie with reversed cyclic order of colours, which cannot occur on the cube.

Moreover, for any three colours that form the three visible faces of a corner cubie, the cyclic order of these colours cannot be altered. For example, suppose that the solved state of the cube under consideration appears as in Figure 4(a). On the corner cubie consisting of the colours red, green, and white, they appear in the clockwise order red–green–white, or equivalently white–red–green or green–white–red (see Figure 5(a)). Any relative colour arrangement that would require a cubie with the reversed cyclic order, as illustrated in Figure 5(b), is therefore not legal.

Proposition 2.2. *The relative positions of all corner cubies in a legal uniform windmill pattern are identical to their relative positions in the solved state of the cube.*

Proof. Suppose that the position and orientation of one corner cubie in the given uniform windmill pattern are known — for instance, the cubie with the colours red, green, and white (see Figure 6). According to the definition of a uniform windmill pattern, the four corner stickers on each face must share the same colour. Hence, the position circled in Figure 6 can only be occupied by a corner cubie whose visible colours, in clockwise order, are “ C , green, red”, where C denotes some colour. The only legitimate corner cubie satisfying this requirement is the one coloured yellow, green, and red. Hence, the corner at the circled position in Figure 6 is uniquely determined.

Figure 6: A configuration of the $4 \times 4 \times 4$ Rubik’s Cube in which the position and orientation of the red–green–white corner cubie are known. The circled position indicates the location of the corner cubie whose identity and orientation are to be determined. All regions irrelevant to the proof are shaded with dots.

By applying the same reasoning to the remaining corners, we can determine the identities and orientations of all the other corner cubies. Moreover, this procedure shows that the relative arrangement of the corner cubies in the pattern coincides with that in the solved state of the cube. \square

Lemma 2.3. *Suppose there exists a legal uniform windmill pattern on the $4 \times 4 \times 4$ Rubik’s Cube. Let B be a branch of an arbitrary windmill in this pattern, and suppose B has colour C . Then B cannot be adjacent to a face of the cube whose background colour is either C itself or the colour opposite to C in the solved state of the cube.*

Proof. Let D be the colour opposite to C in the solved state of the cube. If B were adjacent to a face whose background colour is either C or D , then there would exist an edge cubie either containing two stickers of colour C or containing a C - D pair, both of which are impossible in a standard Rubik’s Cube. \square

Corollary 2.4. *Suppose there is a legal uniform windmill pattern on the $4 \times 4 \times 4$ Rubik’s Cube. Then, on any face of this pattern, for any two windmill branches whose colours are opposite in the solved state of the cube, the two branches must occupy opposite positions on that face.*

Proof. Without loss of generality, we focus on the face whose background colour is red. By Proposition 2.2, the four faces adjacent to it have background colours green,

white, blue, and yellow, as illustrated in Figure 7. According to the requirements of a uniform windmill pattern, the four branches on the red-background face can only take these four colours: green, white, blue, and yellow.

Figure 7: The face of a uniform windmill pattern with a red background. Positions whose colours are undetermined are indicated by dotted areas, while the background colours of the adjacent faces are indicated.

By Lemma 2.3, each of the yellow and white branches can only point upwards or downwards. Hence, the white and yellow branches must be opposite to each other. Similarly, the green and blue branches on the same face must also be opposite. The same reasoning applies to every other face of the cube. \square

C_6	C_6	C_4	C_6
C_5	C_5	C_4	C_6
C_6	C_2	C_3	C_3
C_6	C_2	C_6	C_6

Figure 8: The face that appears after the entire cube is rotated by 180 degrees about its vertical axis.

Proposition 2.5. *Suppose there exists a legal uniform windmill pattern on the $4 \times 4 \times 4$ Rubik’s Cube. Take any face of the pattern as the front face, and assume that it appears as in Figure 1(a). If the entire cube is then rotated by 180° about its vertical axis, then the windmill on the new front face will also have branch colours C_2 , C_3 , C_4 and C_5 . Moreover, the new front face appears as shown in Figure 8, where C_6 denotes the colour opposite to C_1 in the solved state of the cube.*

Proof. By Proposition 2.2, it is clear that C_6 must be the colour opposite to C_1 in the solved state of the cube. We now show that, on the new front face obtained after rotating the entire cube by 180 degrees about its vertical axis, the windmill branch pointing upwards must be of colour C_4 .

Consider Figure 9, which depicts the cube in its original orientation — that is, the front face appears as in Figure 1(a). Note that the branches of colours C_5 and C_3 point to

the left and right, respectively. By Lemma 2.3, the background colours of the left and right faces in Figure 9 can only be C_2 and C_4 (though not necessarily in that order). Consequently, on the new front face — namely, the face appearing after the cube is rotated by 180 degrees about its vertical axis — the colour of the upward-pointing branch must be either C_2 or C_4 . The background colour of the upper face must be either C_3 or C_5 ; as its specific value is irrelevant to the argument, we denote it simply by D .

Figure 9: The cube in an orientation where the front face appears as in Figure 1(a). The hidden face of the circled cubie at the back is shown and labelled C_7 .

For a contradiction, assume that the upward-pointing branch on the new front face is not of colour C_4 . Then, by the reasoning above, it must be of colour C_2 , which means that the sticker labelled C_7 in Figure 9 has colour C_2 . Note that in the standard $4 \times 4 \times 4$ Rubik's Cube, for any two colours A and B that appear on adjacent faces in the solved state, there are exactly two A - B edge cubies. Hence, the circled cubies in Figure 9 are the only two D - C_2 edge cubies in the cube. However, according to their orientations as shown in the figure, one of the D - C_2 edge cubies must have orientation 1. By Theorem 2.1, this implies the given pattern is illegal, which yields a contradiction.

Hence, the sticker labelled C_7 in Figure 9 must be of colour C_4 , and the branch pointing upwards on the new front face must therefore be of colour C_4 . The colours of the remaining windmill branches on that face can be determined in a similar manner. \square

Corollary 2.6. *There are at most 64 different legal uniform windmill patterns on the $4 \times 4 \times 4$ Rubik's Cube.*

Proof. By Proposition 2.2, regardless of how different two uniform windmill patterns may appear, if they are legal, they must share the same background colour arrangement. Any difference between two legal uniform windmill patterns arise solely from the arrangements of their windmill branches.

By the definition of a uniform windmill pattern, once the background colour of a face is fixed, the set of colours appearing on its four windmill branches is completely determined, although the specific branch position corresponding to each colour is not yet known. Furthermore, by Lemma 2.3 and Corollary 2.4, for any two branches of

the same windmill whose colours are opposite in the solved state of the cube, there are only two possible positional arrangements of these branches. Since each face contains two such pairs of opposite-coloured branches, the total number of possible arrangements per face is $2 \times 2 = 4$.

Now consider an arbitrary corner cubie — say, the one with the colours red, green, and white. Let the three faces surrounding this cubie be F_1 , F_2 and F_3 . Each of these faces has four possible arrangements, so together F_1 , F_2 and F_3 yield $4 \times 4 \times 4 = 64$ possibilities. However, by Proposition 2.5, the appearance of any face in a legal uniform windmill pattern uniquely determines the appearance of its opposite face. Therefore, the composite appearance of F_1 , F_2 and F_3 determines the color arrangement of the entire cube. Consequently, there are at most 64 possible uniform windmill patterns on the $4 \times 4 \times 4$ Rubik's Cube. \square

Definition 2.7. A uniform windmill pattern on the $4 \times 4 \times 4$ Rubik's Cube satisfies the **permissibility conditions** if the following hold:

1. All corner cubies used in the pattern exist in the cube. That is, no corner cubie contains two stickers of the same colour or contains two colours that are opposite to each other in the solved state of the cube. Moreover, for any three colours forming the visible faces of a corner cubie, the cyclic order of these colours is correct.
2. For any branch B of any windmill in the pattern, let its colour be C . Then B is not adjacent to any face whose background colour is either C itself or the colour opposite to C in the solved state of the cube.
3. If any face of the pattern is taken as the front face — say, it appears as shown in Figure 1(a) — then, after rotating the entire cube by 180° about its vertical axis, the new front face appears as in Figure 8, where C_6 denotes the colour opposite to C_1 in the solved state of the cube.

By Lemma 2.3 and Proposition 2.5, it is clear that any legal uniform windmill pattern must satisfy the permissibility conditions. We will show that the converse also holds — namely, that any uniform windmill pattern satisfying these conditions is legal. Consequently, it will follow that the 64 patterns enumerated earlier are indeed valid.

Proposition 2.8. *For any uniform windmill pattern that satisfies the permissibility conditions, there exists a configuration of the $4 \times 4 \times 4$ Rubik's Cube representing this pattern, in which every edge cubie has orientation 0.*

Proof. By the first and second conditions stated in Definition 2.7, all cubies involved in the pattern are legitimate. Moreover, by following the argument in the proof of Proposition 2.2, we deduce that every legitimate corner cubie is used exactly once.

For the centre cubies, by the definition of a uniform windmill pattern, we observe that on each face with a fixed background colour, the colours of the four windmill branches — and hence those of the four centre stickers — are determined. For example, the face with a red background must have blue, green, yellow, and white as the colours of its four centre stickers, while the face with a white background must have blue, green, red, and orange, and so on. Altogether, we find that for each colour C appearing on the standard cube, exactly four centre cubies of colour C are used. Consequently, every centre cubie of the standard $4 \times 4 \times 4$ cube is used exactly once.

We now show that every edge cubie can be used exactly once with orientation 0. Consider Figure 3, which depicts the cube in its solved state. We first demonstrate how to use the circled edge cubie in Figure 3 in the given pattern. By the proof of Proposition 2.2, we know that for any colour C appearing on the standard $4 \times 4 \times 4$ Rubik's Cube, there exists a face in the given pattern whose background colour is C . Regardless of the specific pattern, the face with a red background must resemble that in Figure 7, where the background colours of the faces adjacent to the red-background face are indicated.

By the second condition in Definition 2.7, together with the definition of a uniform windmill pattern, the windmill branch B_1 that has a yellow background and is adjacent to the red-background face must be either green or blue. Similarly, the windmill branch B_2 that has a white background and is adjacent to the red-background face must also be either green or blue. However, by Proposition 2.5, B_1 and B_2 cannot share the same colour. Hence, one of them — without loss of generality, B_1 , must be green. If the circled edge cubie shown in Figure 3 is used at the intersection of B_1 and the red-background face, then its orientation is 0.

Note that if the boxed edge cubie in Figure 3 is placed at the intersection of a green windmill branch and the face with red background colour so as to produce the appearance of the intersection in the given pattern, its orientation becomes 1. Hence, the boxed cubie cannot take the role of the circled one and must instead be used at the intersection of a red windmill branch and the face with green background colour. By continuing this reasoning, we see that if every edge cubie is required to have orientation 0, then all the 24 legitimate edge cubies on the cube must appear in the given uniform windmill pattern. Since there are exactly 24 positions in the $4 \times 4 \times 4$ Rubik's Cube that can accommodate edge cubies, the Pigeonhole Principle implies that each legitimate edge cubie is used exactly once. \square

Proposition 2.9. *Any uniform windmill pattern that satisfies the permissibility conditions is legal.*

Proof. We now apply Theorem 2.1. By Proposition 2.8, there exists a configuration C representing the given pattern, in which every edge cubie has orientation 0. Following the argument in the proof of Proposition 2.2, the relative positions of the corner cubies in C coincide with their relative positions in the solved state of the cube. Hence, a new configuration C' can be obtained by rotating the entire cube so that the face with yellow background becomes the front face and the face with red background becomes the upper face.

Note that a global rotation of the $4 \times 4 \times 4$ Rubik's Cube does not change any edge orientation; hence, C' satisfies the first condition stated in Theorem 2.1. Moreover, the orientation value of each corner cubie in C' is 0, so the sum of the corner orientations is 0 modulo 3. As C' represents the given pattern, the claim follows. \square

Theorem 2.10. *There exist exactly 64 distinct legal uniform windmill patterns on the $4 \times 4 \times 4$ Rubik's Cube.*

Proof. By Proposition 2.2, the arrangement of the background colours of all faces is already determined. Hence we only need to arrange the colours of the windmill branches. Choose an arbitrary corner cubie and let the three faces surrounding it be F_1 , F_2 and F_3 . It is straightforward to verify that any uniform windmill pattern constructed according to the following procedure satisfies the permissibility conditions:

1. Assign the colours of the windmill branches on F_1 , F_2 and F_3 , so that on each of these faces, the arrangement satisfies the two conditions stated in Definition 1.1 and the second condition stated in Definition 2.7.
2. Arrange the colours on the faces opposite to F_1 , F_2 and F_3 according to the third condition stated in Definition 2.7.

In the first step, there are 64 possible choices, while the second step is completely determined by the first. Consequently, we can obtain 64 different uniform windmill patterns using the procedure above. Moreover, these patterns satisfy the permissibility conditions and so are legal by Proposition 2.9. Finally, by Corollary 2.6, these 64 configurations are precisely all the distinct legal uniform windmill patterns on the $4 \times 4 \times 4$ Rubik's Cube. \square

3 Algorithms and Total Symmetry

The previous section has established the theoretical basis for the existence of 64 distinct legal uniform windmill patterns on the $4 \times 4 \times 4$ Rubik's Cube. In this section, we present the specific algorithms — that is, the explicit sequences of legal moves — by which these patterns can be physically realised. We adopt the standard international notations for cube operations. For example, R denotes a 90° clockwise rotation of the right face, F' denotes a 90° anticlockwise rotation of the front face, $B2$ denotes a 180° rotation of the back face, Rw denotes a 90° clockwise rotation of the two right layers, y denotes a 90° clockwise rotation of the entire cube about the vertical axis, and y^2 denotes a 180° rotation of the entire cube about the same axis.

Proposition 3.1. *Suppose we have a solved $4 \times 4 \times 4$ Rubik's Cube whose planar net is as shown in Figure 4(a). Then no matter what the initial orientation of the cube is — that is, no matter which face is initially taken as the front or top — if we perform the following algorithm:*

$$B2, L, U, R', D2, L', U2, R, B2, R', U', F', R, B, F', D, F2, L', Rw2, Fw2, U2, R, F2, U2, Rw2, R', D, Rw2, Fw', Uw2, R', D, U, L', Rw', Fw2, D, Fw2, Uw2, B,$$

then the resulting pattern will be identical to that shown in Figure 4(b). (Recall that we regard two patterns of the cube as identical if one can be obtained from the other by a rotation of the entire cube.)

Proof. This statement can be verified empirically by applying the above sequence to a standard $4 \times 4 \times 4$ Rubik's Cube and observing the resulting pattern. To confirm that the outcome remains identical regardless of the cube's initial orientation, one could, in principle, apply the algorithm to all the possible orientations and verify that the final patterns are indeed the same. Although this method is valid, it is evidently tedious. Later, when the concept of “total symmetry” is introduced, a far simpler theoretical justification will become apparent. \square

Proposition 3.2. *Consider a standard $4 \times 4 \times 4$ Rubik's Cube exhibiting a legal uniform windmill pattern. If the following algorithm is applied:*

$$R', L', Uw2, R, L, Bw2, Rw2, Bw2, B2, r2, B2, F2, l2, F2, y2,$$

then, on the front face, the colours of the windmill branches pointing upwards and downwards are interchanged. Also, on the back face, the colours of the upward and downward branches are swapped. All other colour arrangements — namely, the background colours of the faces and the colours of all the other branches — remain unchanged. In particular, the outcome is a legal uniform windmill pattern.

Proof. We can verify empirically that, after applying the algorithm, the positions and orientations of all cubies in the outermost right and left layers remain identical to their initial positions and orientations. Hence, the only remaining part to examine is the colours of the stickers on the inner right and left slices.

By the definition of a uniform windmill pattern and Proposition 2.5, the colour arrangement on these inner right and left slices, for any legal uniform windmill pattern, must appear as shown in Figure 10, where identical labels indicate identical colours. C_6 (respectively, C_{12}) is the colour opposite to C_1 (respectively, C_7) when the cube is solved.

Figure 10: The appearance of the inner right and left slices in a legal uniform windmill pattern.

Note that the planar net of the Rubik's Cube has the form of a cross, consisting of one horizontal and one vertical strip. We take the cube face located at the intersection of these two strips to be the front face, and we assume that, in Figure 10, the face shown at the top corresponds to the upper face. The only remaining point to verify is that, after performing the algorithm, every C_2 in Figure 10 becomes C_4 , and every C_4 becomes C_2 , while the colours of all the other labelled places are unchanged. This can likewise be confirmed empirically, and the detailed verification is therefore omitted here. \square

Note that, by the definition of a uniform windmill pattern, once the background colour of a cube face is known, the colours of the four windmill branches on that face are also determined, although their specific positions may remain undetermined. Moreover, by Lemma 2.3, in any legal uniform windmill pattern, for any windmill branch whose colour is known, even if the exact position of that branch is unknown, we can still determine whether it is horizontal or vertical on the given face.

As a consequence, for any two legal uniform windmill patterns U_1 and U_2 , U_1 can be transformed into U_2 through a finite sequence of transformations T_1, \dots, T_n , where each T_i ($i = 1, \dots, n$) represents the interchange of the colours of two opposite branches on some face, followed by a corresponding change of the appearance of the opposite face, so that the third condition stated in Definition 2.7 is satisfied.

Now let G denote the group generated by the algorithm stated in Proposition 3.2 and all global rotations of the cube. For any configuration C that represents a legal uniform windmill pattern, it follows from Proposition 3.2 and the above discussion that the orbit

$$GU := \{O(U) \mid O \in G\},$$

modulo the equivalence relation identifying configurations that are visually identical up to global rotations, represents the set of all legal uniform windmill patterns on the $4 \times 4 \times 4$ Rubik's Cube.

The following definition may at first seem abstract, but its meaning will become clear through the examples that follow.

Definition 3.3. Let B be a windmill branch in a legal uniform windmill pattern on the $4 \times 4 \times 4$ Rubik's Cube, and suppose B is coloured C . We define the **clockwise return angle** of B by the following procedure:

1. Rotate the entire cube so that the face containing B becomes the front face.
2. Identify the face F that is adjacent to the front face and whose background colour is C .
3. The clockwise return angle of B is then defined as the smallest angle of rotation (say A) such that, when B is rotated clockwise through A , it points towards the direction of F .

For example, suppose that, in a legal uniform windmill pattern, a yellow windmill branch B lies on the face whose background colour is red. To determine the clockwise return angle of B , we first rotate the entire cube so that the face with red background becomes the front face. Assume that the background colours of the faces adjacent to the front face are known, as illustrated in Figure 7.

If B points upwards, then, in order for B to point towards the face whose background colour is yellow, it must be rotated 270 degrees clockwise. Hence, the clockwise return angle of B is 270°. If B points downwards in Figure 7, then B must be rotated 90 degrees clockwise to point towards the yellow face; in this case, the clockwise return angle of B is 90°.

Note that, by Lemma 2.3, in a legal uniform windmill pattern, the clockwise return angle of a windmill branch can never be 0° or 180°.

Definition 3.4. A legal uniform windmill pattern is said to be **totally symmetric** (or to **satisfy total symmetry**) if the clockwise return angles of all windmill branches in the pattern have the same degree.

For example, the uniform windmill pattern shown in Figure 4(b) is totally symmetric, since one can verify that, for every windmill branch appearing in the pattern, the clockwise return angle is 90° . We now state and prove the fundamental property of a totally symmetric legal uniform windmill pattern.

Theorem 3.5. *For any legal uniform windmill pattern, the following statements are equivalent:*

- *The pattern is totally symmetric.*
- *Given an arbitrary algorithm — that is, a sequence of legal moves on the $4 \times 4 \times 4$ Rubik's Cube — which transforms a solved cube into the given pattern. Then, regardless of the initial orientation of the solved cube, applying that algorithm always produces the given pattern.*

Proof. The proof relies on the observation that, for a solved Rubik's Cube, the choice of which face is regarded as the front or the top carries no mathematical significance. Whatever occurs after performing a given algorithm under one initial orientation of the cube, analogous transformations must occur if the same algorithm is applied under another initial orientation.

Assume that the given pattern satisfies total symmetry, and suppose there exists an algorithm which transforms a solved cube into this pattern when the cube is held in a particular initial orientation. Then, by symmetry, if we start from any other initial orientation and perform the same algorithm, the result will again be a uniform windmill pattern.

In the given pattern, the clockwise return angles of all windmill branches share the same degree d . Hence, by symmetry, in the pattern obtained from a different initial orientation, all windmill branches must also have clockwise return angles of degree d . This implies that the pattern obtained from any orientation is identical to the given pattern.

Now assume that the given pattern is not totally symmetric. Then there exist two windmill branches, B_1 and B_2 , with colours C_1 and C_2 and background colours D_1 and D_2 respectively, such that B_1 and B_2 have clockwise return angles of different degrees. Let these degrees be d and e respectively, where $d \neq e$.

By symmetry, we can deduce that there exists an orientation of the solved cube such that, if we start from this orientation and apply the same algorithm, the windmill branch with colour C_1 and background colour D_1 will have a clockwise return angle of degree e . This implies that the resulting pattern is distinct from the given pattern, since in the original pattern the branch with colour C_1 and background colour D_1 has a clockwise return angle of degree d , with $d \neq e$. □

With Theorem 3.5 established, Proposition 3.1 follows immediately, since the uniform windmill pattern shown in Figure 4(b) is totally symmetric. In fact, Theorem 3.5 can be reached quite intuitively: total symmetry implies that each colour on the Rubik's Cube is arranged in exactly the same way. Consequently, for a totally symmetric uniform windmill pattern, it is plausible that the validity of any algorithm does not depend on the initial orientation of the cube.

More specifically, consider the pattern shown in Figure 4(b). Let the face with a red background be the front face, and imagine enlarging the back face and shrinking the

front face so that five faces — including the front — are simultaneously visible (see Figure 11(a)). Figure 11(a) then illustrates how the colour red is arranged in this uniform windmill pattern. If the yellow-background face is taken as the front face and the same action is performed, we obtain Figure 11(b).

Figure 11: Appearances of the $4 \times 4 \times 4$ Rubik's Cube obtained by shrinking the front face and enlarging the back face. Regions irrelevant to the discussion are shaded with dots. (a) The appearance obtained by taking the red-background face as the front face. (b) The appearance obtained by taking the yellow-background face as the front face.

Superimposing Figures 11(a) and 11(b) shows that the red and yellow stickers coincide exactly. A similar check confirms that every other colour in the pattern is arranged in the same way. Moreover, in any totally symmetric uniform windmill pattern that is distinct from that in Figure 4(b), we again find that all colours share the same arrangement. This demonstrates that a totally symmetric uniform windmill pattern is a particular instance of what [3] termed a **colour equality pattern**. For the precise and formal definition of a colour equality pattern, the reader is referred to [3].

Are there any legal uniform windmill patterns that are colour equality patterns but not totally symmetric? If so, how many such patterns exist? Also, for patterns that are not uniform windmill patterns, when are their generating algorithms independent of the cube's initial orientation? These remain open questions for interested readers.

Theorem 3.6. *There are exactly two distinct legal uniform windmill patterns on the $4 \times 4 \times 4$ Rubik's Cube that satisfy total symmetry.*

Proof. By Proposition 2.2, the arrangement of the background colours is fixed. By Lemma 2.3, in any legal uniform windmill pattern, and for any windmill branch within it, the clockwise return angle can only be 90° or 270° . However, once the clockwise return angle of one windmill branch is known, the clockwise return angles of all other branches are consequently determined in order to achieve total symmetry. Hence, the appearance of the entire cube is uniquely determined. Therefore, there exist two possible uniform windmill patterns that satisfy total symmetry.

Both of these patterns satisfy the permissibility conditions; thus, by Proposition 2.9, we may conclude that there are precisely two distinct legal uniform windmill patterns on the $4 \times 4 \times 4$ Rubik's Cube that satisfy total symmetry. \square

4 Conclusions and Further Questions

In this paper, we have formally defined uniform clockwise colour-separated windmill patterns with pairwise distinct branch colours on the $4 \times 4 \times 4$ Rubik's Cube. We have proved that there are exactly 64 distinct legal uniform windmill patterns and have introduced algorithms that generate them. Finally, we introduced the concept of total symmetry and showed that totally symmetric legal uniform windmill patterns are precisely examples of [3]'s colour equality patterns. Furthermore, we have proved that there are exactly two distinct legal uniform windmill patterns that satisfy total symmetry, which demonstrates the rarity of perfect beauty and symmetry.

Figure 12: A paper windmill made by the author, which rotates clockwise when blown. Note that this windmill picture can be represented on the face of a $4 \times 4 \times 4$ Rubik's Cube in the way shown in Figure 2.

Beyond the mathematical results, the construction also embodies aesthetic considerations. Windmill patterns resemble real-life windmills, giving the design an artistic quality. To ensure that each cube face appears colourful and visually pleasing, we have required the four branches of every windmill in the pattern to have pairwise distinct colours. We have also adopted an artistic principle whereby adjacent regions should not share identical or similar colours, allowing the different parts of the pattern to remain easily distinguishable. In addition, all windmills in the pattern have been required to share the same orientation, imparting an additional sense of unity and symmetry to the overall construction.

However, the discussion does not end here. If some of the aesthetic constraints are relaxed, new questions arise. For example, what happens if two branches of the same windmill share the same colour, or if a branch is allowed to have the same colour as its background? How many legal patterns would then exist? Moreover, for higher-order Rubik's Cubes, how might similar windmill patterns be designed so that the resulting patterns both resemble real windmills and remain visually pleasing as well as legal? These are left as open questions for the interested reader.

Acknowledgements: The author first discovered the pattern shown in Figure 4(b) independently, by performing legal moves on the Rubik's Cube without any external

assistance. This initial construction took nearly one hour. Subsequently, the *Cube Solver* application developed by the company LOLAGRE was used to obtain a more efficient algorithm for generating the pattern in Figure 4(b), as presented in Proposition 3.1. The first eight steps of the algorithm stated in Proposition 3.2 were obtained using the same application. During the preparation of this manuscript, the author used *ChatGPT (GPT-5, OpenAI)* solely for language refinement and for improving the clarity and fluency of English expressions. The author has carefully reviewed and revised all generated text and takes full responsibility for the content of this paper.

Figure 13: A $4 \times 4 \times 4$ Rubik's Cube displaying a uniform windmill pattern, viewed from different directions.

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